

1 **Over-expression of the periplasmic nitrate reductase supports**
2 **anaerobic growth by *Ensifer meliloti***

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18 **Keywords**

19 Denitrification, gene expression, nitrate, nitrite, nitric oxide, nitrous oxide

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22 In this work, we demonstrate by the first time that over-expression of the *E. meliloti*
23 periplasmic nitrate reductase allows this partial denitrifier to grow by nitrate respiration
24 through the denitrification process.

33

34 **ABSTRACT**

35 The alfalfa endosymbiont *Ensifer meliloti* strain1021 is known to be an incomplete
36 denitrifier due to its inability to grow anoxically using nitrate as respiratory substrate to
37 produce ATP and grow under anoxic conditions. Although this bacterium contains and
38 expresses the complete set of denitrification genes *napEFDABC*, *nirK*, *norECBQD* and
39 *nosRZDFYLYX* encoding the periplasmic nitrate reductase (Nap), Cu-containing nitrite
40 reductase (NirK), c-type nitric oxide (cNor) and nitrous oxide reductase (Nos),
41 respectively, the reasons of its inability to grow under anoxic conditions are still very
42 poorly understood. In the present study, we have constructed an *E. meliloti* strain over-
43 expressing *napEFDABC* genes (Nap⁺) and demonstrated that this strain is able to grow
44 through anaerobic nitrate respiration. Furthermore, Nap⁺ showed increased NapC levels
45 as well as Nap, Nir, and cNor activities and higher capacity to produce NO and N₂O
46 compared to wild-type cells. These results suggest that the inability of *E. meliloti* to
47 grow under anaerobic conditions using nitrate as electron acceptor is attributable to a
48 limitation in the expression of the periplasmic nitrate reductase.

49

50 INTRODUCTION

51 Under oxygen limiting conditions, many bacterial species can switch from O₂-
52 respiration to nitrate (NO₃⁻)-respiration through the denitrification process to produce
53 energy which enable facultative aerobic bacteria to survive and multiply anoxically. The
54 complete denitrification pathway comprises the dissimilatory reduction of nitrate NO₃⁻
55 or nitrite (NO₂⁻) to molecular nitrogen (N₂) through the formation of the gaseous
56 intermediates nitric oxide (NO) and nitrous oxide (N₂O). NO contributes to the
57 depletion of the ozone layer and is also a potent cytotoxic gas as well as a key signal
58 molecule. N₂O is a powerful greenhouse gas (GHG) which, based on its radiative
59 capacity, possesses a global warming potential 300-fold greater than CO₂ and can
60 persist for up to 150 years in the atmosphere (IPCC, 2014). Denitrification reactions are
61 catalyzed by a periplasmic (Nap) or membrane-bound (Nar) nitrate reductase, nitrite
62 reductases (NirK/NirS), nitric oxide reductases (cNor, qNor, Cu_ANor) and nitrous oxide
63 reductase (Nos) encoded by *nar/nap*, *nir*, *nor* and *nos* genes, respectively, which are
64 expressed under oxygen limiting conditions and in the presence of NO₃⁻ or a nitrogen
65 oxide (NO_x) (Torres *et al.*, 2016; van Spanning, 2007; Zumft, 1997). Most denitrifiers
66 have Nap and Nar enzymes. Nar functions as a respiratory enzyme, however Nap has
67 different physiological roles including the dissipation of the excess of reducing power
68 during aerobic growth with reduced carbon substrates and also catalyzes the anaerobic
69 nitrate respiration during ammonification or denitrification processes (reviewed by
70 Richardson *et al.*, 2007; Richardson, 2011; Simon and Klotz, 2013).

71 Some bacteria collectively known as rhizobia that have the capacity to fix N₂
72 during symbiotic associations with legume plants through the formation of nodules in
73 their roots also contain denitrification genes in their genomes. Among them,
74 *Bradyrhizobium diazoefficiens*, the endosymbiont of soybeans, is the only rhizobial

75 species that has the ability to grow through anoxic nitrate respiration where
76 denitrification has been extensively studied (Bedmar *et al.*, 2005; Bedmar *et al.*, 2013;
77 Delgado *et al.*, 2007; Torres *et al.*, 2016). In this bacterium, Nap is the only nitrate
78 reductase that supports nitrate respiration and initiates the denitrification pathway
79 (Delgado *et al.*, 2003).

80 *Ensifer* (formerly *Sinorhizobium*) *meliloti* is able to perform N₂-fixing symbiotic
81 associations with legumes from the *Medicago*, *Melilotus*, and *Trigonella* genera. To
82 cope with the low oxygen concentration (10-50 nM) in the nodules, some rhizobia
83 species including *E. meliloti* have the capacity to express denitrification enzymes in the
84 bacteroids (Bedmar *et al.*, 2013; Horchani *et al.*, 2011; Torres *et al.*, 2016). In fact, *E.*
85 *meliloti* 1021 possesses the complete set of the denitrification genes including
86 *napEFDABC*, *nirK*, *norECBQD* and *nosRZDFYLX* genes encoding Nap, the copper-
87 containing nitrite reductase (NirK), the c-type nitric oxide reductase (cNor) and Nos,
88 respectively (Galibert *et al.*, 2001; Torres *et al.*, 2011). However, this rhizobial species
89 is known to be a partial denitrifier due to its incapacity to grow via nitrate respiration
90 under free-living anoxic conditions (Bueno *et al.*, 2015; Torres *et al.*, 2011; Torres *et*
91 *al.*, 2014). Despite the inability of *E. meliloti* to grow anoxically with NO₃⁻, *napA*, *nirK*,
92 *norC* and *nosZ* denitrification genes are expressed in cells subjected to anoxic
93 conditions with nitrate (Torres *et al.*, 2014). In the latter studies, induction of *E. meliloti*
94 *napA* expression was remarkable lower in comparison to that of *nirK*, *norC* and *nosZ*
95 expression in response to anoxia and nitrate (Torres *et al.*, 2014). Based on these
96 observations, we suspected that a limitation in the *E. meliloti nap* induction during
97 anoxic incubation with nitrate might be the reason to explain the *E. meliloti* incapability
98 to grow under these conditions. This hypothesis gained strength by the fact that in the
99 model rhizobia denitrifier *B. diazoefficiens* Nap is the sole nitrate reductase that

100 supports nitrate respiration and growth under anaerobic conditions (Delgado *et al.*,
101 2003).

102 In this work, we have constructed an *E. meliloti* strain over-expressing
103 *napEFDABC* genes (Nap⁺) and we have demonstrated that this strain is able to grow
104 through anaerobic nitrate respiration. Furthermore, we have performed a complete
105 genetic and physiological characterization of the Nap⁺ strain and we observed a
106 significant induction of Nap expression as well as increased levels of Nap, Nir, and
107 cNor activities in the Nap⁺ strain compared to wild-type cells. These results support our
108 hypothesis and allow us to propose that the inability of *E. meliloti* to grow under
109 anaerobic conditions from nitrate respiration might be due to a limitation in the
110 induction of the *napEFDABC* genes in response to anoxia and nitrate.

111

112 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

113 **Bacterial strains and growth conditions**

114 The wild-type strain *Ensifer meliloti* 1021 (Meade *et al.*, 1982) was used in this study.
115 To generate the *napEFDABC* over-expressing derivative Sm4002, a 4709 bp fragment
116 covering the genomic region corresponding to the *napEFDABC* operon and 36 and 42
117 nucleotides belonging to the up and downstream regions, respectively, was amplified by
118 PCR using the oligos pair *nap_sobr_For/nap_sobr_Rev* (Table S1). The PCR products
119 were subsequently cloned as a BamHI/EcoRI fragment into pBBR1-MCS2 (Kovach *et*
120 *al.*, 1995), yielding plasmid pDS4002. After corroborating the integrity of the cloned
121 fragment by sequencing using the internal oligos *nap_sobr_IN1_For*,
122 *nap_sobr_IN1.5_For*, *nap_sobr_IN2_For*, *nap_sobr_IN2.5_For*, *nap_sobr_IN3_For*,
123 *nap_sobr_IN4_For*, and *nap_sobr_Rev* (Table S1), pDS4002 was conjugated with *E.*

124 *meliloti* 1021 obtaining the strain Sm4002 which is able to express constitutively the
125 *napEFDABC* genes.

126 *Escherichia coli* cells DH5 α (Sambrook *et al.*, 1989) or S17.1 (Simon *et al.*,
127 1983) were cultivated in Luria Bertani medium (Miller *et al.*, 1972) at 37° C. *E. meliloti*
128 strains were cultivated routinely under aerobic conditions at 30°C in Tryptone Yeast
129 complete medium (Beringer, 1974) to obtain cellular mass. Subsequent growth
130 experiments under anoxic conditions were carried out using minimum medium (
131 Robertsen *et al.*, 1981) with (MMN) or without (MM) 10 mM KNO₃. Anoxic
132 conditions were reached by incubating the cells in completed filled 200 ml bottles or 17
133 ml tubes. Antibiotics used in *E. meliloti* cultures were added at the following
134 concentrations ($\mu\text{g} \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$): streptomycin, 200; kanamycin, 200.

135

136 **Determination of nitrate and nitrite reductase activity**

137 After incubation of the cells anoxically in MMN medium during 24 h at an initial OD₆₀₀
138 of about 0.15-0.2, methyl viologen-dependent nitrate reductase (MV⁺-NR) and nitrite
139 reductase (MV⁺-Nir) activities were determined according to Delgado *et al.* (2003) and
140 Bueno *et al.* (2005), respectively.

141

142 **Analytical methods**

143 Nitrite concentration was analyzed according to Nicholas and Nason (1957). To
144 estimate the concentration of proteins, we used the Bio-Rad reagent. Increasing known
145 concentrations of bovine serum albumin (BSA) were used as standards.

146

147 **Haem-staining analysis**

148 After incubation in MM or MMN medium during 24 h under anoxic conditions (initial
149 OD₆₀₀ of 0.15-0.2), cells were broken in a French Press (SLM Aminco, Jessup, MD,
150 USA) with a constant pressure of about 120 MPa. Membranes isolation and proteins
151 separation and transference to a nitrocellulose membrane were performed according to
152 Delgado *et al.*(2003). Then, proteins were stained for haem-dependent peroxidase
153 activity using the chemiluminiscence detection method previously described by Vargas
154 *et al.*(1993).

155

156 **Determination of nitric oxide and nitrous oxide production capacity**

157 Cells were cultured anoxically during 24 h in MMN medium (initial OD₆₀₀ of 0.15-0.2).
158 Then, cells were harvested and nitric oxide (NO) consumption activity as well as the
159 NO production capacity were determined in a reaction chamber using a 2-mm ISONOP
160 electrode following the methodology described by Torres *et al.*(2014). Nitrous oxide
161 (N₂O) production was measured by gas chromatography according to Torres and
162 colleagues (2014).

163

164 **Quantitative Real-Time PCR Analysis**

165 Total RNA was purified from anoxically cultivated *E. meliloti* cells in MMN using the
166 methodology previously described by Torres *et al.* (2014). After treatment of isolated
167 RNA with DNase (Qiagen), RNA quantity and quality was checked according to
168 Sambrook *et al.*(1989). Then, 1 mg of total RNA, random hexamers and SuperScript II
169 reverse transcriptase (Invitrogen) were used for cDNA synthesis following the
170 supplier's instructions. Real-time PCR analyses were performed in an iQTM5 Optical
171 System (Bio-Rad, Foster City, CA, United States) using a reaction mixture of a total
172 volume of 19 ml containing 9.5 ml of iQTM SYBR Green Supermix (Bio-Rad), 2 mM

173 of the *napA* primers previously reported by Torres and coworkers (2014), and the
174 cDNA samples. The specificity of the each amplification reaction was verified by
175 generation of melt curves. Expression of the *sMC00128* gene was used as reference
176 for normalization and changes in *napA* expression were analyzed according to Pfaffl
177 (2001).

178

179 **Statistical analysis**

180 The total numbers of replicates are given in each figure and table. Results were analysed
181 by one-way ANOVA, and means were separated using the Tukey HSD test at $P \leq 0.05$
182 with SPSS software.

183

184 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

185 **Over-expression of *E. meliloti napEFDABC* genes**

186 *E. meliloti* 1021 has been considered for many years to be a partial denitrifier due to its
187 incapacity to grow anoxically with nitrate as respiratory substrate (Bueno *et al.*, 2015;
188 Torres *et al.*, 2014). It has become apparent that in some rhizobial species such as *B.*
189 *diazoefficiens*, the respiratory reduction of nitrate to nitrite occurs via the periplasmic
190 nitrate reductase (Nap) which constitutes the first step of the denitrification pathway
191 (Delgado *et al.*, 2003). *E. meliloti* 1021 possesses and expresses *napEFDABC*, *nirK*,
192 *norECBQD* and *nosRZDFYLX* denitrification genes in response to anoxia and nitrate
193 (Torres *et al.*, 2014). However, anoxic *napA* expression was induced only 4-times
194 compared to induction levels of about 49, 84 and 33-times observed by *nirK*, *norC* and
195 *nosZ* genes, respectively, in response to anoxia and nitrate (Torres *et al.*, 2014). These
196 observations allowed us to suggest that the *E. meliloti* incapability to grow anoxically
197 with nitrate might be due to a limitation in *nap* expression under these conditions. To

198 demonstrate this hypothesis, in this work we have constructed the strain Sm4002 with a
199 constitutive expression of *napEFDABC* genes. Firstly, we studied *napA* expression in *E.*
200 *meliloti* 1021 and the Nap⁺ over-expressing strain Sm4002 by performing qRT-PCR
201 analyses using RNA isolated from cells cultured under anoxic conditions in the
202 presence or in absence of nitrate. Figure 1A shows that *napA* expression under anoxic
203 conditions was clearly higher in Sm4002 cells relative to *napA* expression in 1021 cells
204 either in the absence or in the presence of nitrate (fold change of *napA* around 14.3- and
205 10.8-fold, respectively). The weak response of *napA* expression to nitrate in the wild-
206 type strain confirms previous findings (Torres *et al.*, 2014). Haem *c* staining analyses of
207 membranes from *E. meliloti* 1021 cells incubated under anoxic conditions without
208 nitrate revealed the presence of a 25 kDa stained band which probably corresponds to
209 NapC (Fig. 1B, lane 1). Similarly, in other rhizobia species, such as *B. diazoefficiens*,
210 NapC has been identified by haem *c*-staining analyses as a protein of approximately 25
211 kDa (Delgado *et al.*, 2003). This protein was slightly induced in *E. meliloti* wild-type
212 cells incubated anoxically with nitrate compared to those cells incubated without nitrate
213 (Fig. 1B, lane 3) confirming the weak induction of *napA* expression by nitrate (Fig. 1A).
214 However, a strong induction of NapC expression was observed in membranes from the
215 Nap⁺ strain compared to the expression levels detected in *E. meliloti* wild-type cells,
216 after anoxic incubation either in the presence or the absence of nitrate in the medium
217 (Fig. 1B, lanes 2 and 4). In addition to the 25 kDa *c*-type cytochrome, four proteins of
218 about 40, 33, 32 and 27 kDa were also present in membranes from *E. meliloti* 1021 and
219 Sm4002 cells incubated anoxically with or without nitrate (Fig. 1B). These observations
220 confirm previous findings reported by Torres and colleagues (2013; 2014). In the latter
221 studies, the 40 kDa and 33 kDa proteins could not be identified, however, the 32 kDa
222 and 27 kDa *c*-type cytochromes corresponded to the *E. meliloti* FixP and FixO subunits

223 of the *cbb₃*-type high-affinity cytochrome *c* oxidase which is synthesized by the
224 *fixNOQP* genes (Torres *et al.*, 2013).

225 **Nitrate-dependent anoxic growth of *E. meliloti* Nap⁺ over-expressing strain**

226 To unravel the involvement of the Nap⁺ strain in the capability of *E. meliloti* to grow
227 anoxically by using nitrate as electron acceptor, 1021 and Sm4002 cells were incubated
228 under anoxic conditions in MMN and their growth was determined by monitoring the
229 optical density at 600 nm (OD₆₀₀) (Fig. 2A). Confirming previous results (Torres *et al.*,
230 2011; 2014), *E. meliloti* 1021 cells were completely unable to growth under anoxic
231 conditions in the presence of nitrate (Fig. 2A). However, cells of Sm4002 strain were
232 capable to grow anoxically with nitrate reaching an OD at 600 nm of around 0.6 after
233 120 hours incubation (Fig. 2A). These results demonstrate that the inability of *E.*
234 *meliloti* 1021 strain to grow anoxically with nitrate is clearly due to a limitation of Nap
235 expression. In this work, we have obtained for the first time an *E. meliloti* strain able to
236 grow anoxically from nitrate respiration.

237 As shown in Figure 2B, *E. meliloti* wild-type cells incubated anoxically with
238 nitrate accumulated nitrite in the medium during the first 12 hours, decreasing its
239 concentration to zero after 36 h incubation. However, nitrite levels accumulated in the
240 incubation medium of Nap⁺ during the first 12 h were 3.6 higher than those detected in
241 the medium of the parental strain (Fig. 2B). In the case of Nap⁺ cells, nitrite was further
242 consumed during the next 108 h of incubation. These observations suggest that the
243 capacity of nitrite production *in vivo* by Sm4002 was significantly higher than that of
244 the wild-type strain probably due to an induction of Nap activity. This induction might
245 be a consequence of the higher NapC expression levels detected in membranes from the
246 Nap⁺ strain compared to wild-type cells (Fig. 1B).

247 **Activity of denitrification enzymes in the *E. meliloti* Nap⁺ over-expressing strain**

248 To demonstrate that the ability of Sm4002 strain to grow anoxically from nitrate
249 respiration was supported by the denitrification process, we also analyzed in this strain
250 the activity of the Nap, Nir, Nor and Nos denitrification enzymes after incubation of the
251 cells under anoxic conditions with nitrate. As shown in Table 1, cells of the Nap⁺ strain
252 showed about 40-fold higher levels of MV⁺-NR activity compared to those observed in
253 the wild-type cells after 24 h incubation. These results suggest that the growth capacity
254 of strain Sm4002 under anoxic conditions with nitrate could be explained by the
255 significant induction of MV⁺-NR activity compared to wild-type levels. The increased
256 values of Nap activity observed in the Nap⁺ strain correlated with a higher NapC level
257 (Fig. 1B) as well as *napA* expression (Fig. 1A) in this strain compared to those observed
258 in the wild-type strain.

259 Likewise for NR activity, MV⁺-Nir activity reached in cells of the Nap⁺ strain
260 was 100-fold higher than that detected in the parental strain under the same denitrifying
261 growth conditions (Table 1). Moreover, when we measured nitric oxide reductase
262 activity by analyzing NO consumption capacity of Nap⁺ cells after 24 h incubation
263 anoxically with nitrate, this activity was about 10-fold higher respect to the values
264 achieved by the wild-type cells incubated under the same conditions (Table 1).

265 Finally, we determined the capacity of the *E. meliloti* Sm4002 strain to produce
266 NO and N₂O. As shown in Figure 3, NO as well as N₂O production were around 10-
267 and 6.5-fold higher in the Nap⁺ strain compare to those values reached in the wild-type
268 cells cultured anoxically with nitrate (Fig. 3A, B).

269 Taken together, the results obtained in this work demonstrate that the inability of
270 *E. meliloti* 1021 to grow under anoxic conditions from nitrate respiration is attributable
271 to a limitation in Nap expression. Consequently, the cells are probably unable to

272 synthesize a minimum of denitrification proteome due to a limitation in energy
273 production. A similar phenomenon has been recently reported in batch cultures of the
274 model organism *Paracoccus denitrificans*. In this bacterium, it has been observed that
275 the cells suffer an entrapment when O₂ is exhausted and only few cell population of
276 *Paracoccus denitrificans* is able to switch to denitrification, due to a limitation in the
277 transcription of the *nirS* gene, encoding the denitrification enzyme NirS (Hassan *et al.*,
278 2014).

279 Our results expand the understanding of the factors involved in the inability of *E.*
280 *meliloti* to grow by using nitrate as electron acceptor. This knowledge will be
281 instrumental for the selection of competitive and efficient N₂-fixers inoculants that have
282 also de capacity to survive in anoxic environments, such as those encountered in water
283 logged soils, by switching from O₂-respiration to NO₃⁻-respiration. The impact of this
284 capacity in the symbiotic interaction with alfalfa is under investigation.

285 **Conflict of Interest Statement**

286 The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest regarding the publication of this
287 paper, including any commercial, financial, personal or other relationships with other
288 organizations.

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389 **Table 1**

390 Methy viologen-dependent (MV⁺) nitrate reductase (MV⁺-NR), and nitrite reductase
 391 (MV⁺-NiR) activities and nitric oxide reductase (Nor) activity of *E. meliloti* 1021 (WT),
 392 and Sm4002 (Nap⁺), incubated in MMN under anoxic conditions.

Strain	Genotype	Anoxic conditions + 10mM NO ₃ ⁻		
		^a MV ⁺ -NR	^b MV ⁺ -NiR	^c Nor
1021	WT	52.01 (2.54)	3.06 (0.44)	96.50 (10.09)
Sm4002	<i>nap</i> ⁺	2161.81 (104.61)	306.10 (15.41)	977.23 (144.18)

393
 394 ^aMV⁺-NR and ^bMV⁺-NiR activities are given as nmol NO₂⁻ produced or consumed · mg
 395 protein⁻¹ · min⁻¹. ^cNor activity is expressed as nmol NO consumed · mg protein⁻¹ · min⁻¹.
 396 All activities were determined after 18 hours incubation. Data are means with the
 397 standard error in parentheses from at least two different cultures, assayed in triplicate.
 398 -NiR ^cNor

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412 **Figure 1**

413 (A) Expression of *napA* using qRT-PCR analyses with total RNA samples from cells of
414 *E. meliloti* 1021 and Sm4002 strains incubated for 24 h in MM or MMN under anoxic
415 conditions. qRT-PCR reactions were performed with cDNA synthesized from three
416 independent RNA samples assayed in three parallel reactions. Relative expression
417 values refer to differences of *napA* expression relative to WT cells incubated in the
418 absence of nitrate. Bars represent the means with the standard deviations separated
419 using the Tukey HSD test at $P \leq 0.05$. (B) Haem-stained proteins of membranes prepared
420 from *E. meliloti* 1021 (lanes 1 and 3) and Sm4002 (lanes 2 and 4) incubated in MM
421 (lanes 1 and 2) or MMN (lanes 3 and 4) for 24 h under anoxic conditions. Each lane
422 contains 25 μ g of membrane proteins. Haem-stained *c*-type cytochromes identified
423 previously (FixP and FixO) as well as the predicted NapC protein are specified in the
424 right margin. Apparent protein molecular masses (kDa) are shown in the left margin.

425 **Figure 2**

426 (A) Growth of *E. meliloti* 1021 (circles) and Sm4002 (squares) in MM (open symbols)
427 or MMN (full symbols) under anoxic conditions (B) Extracellular nitrite concentration
428 in the incubation medium of *E. meliloti* 1021 (black circles) and Sm4002 strains (black
429 squares). Representative curves of three independent experiments run in triplicate are
430 shown, means with the standard deviations were separated using the Tukey HSD test at
431 $P \leq 0.05$.

432 **Figure 3**

433 (A) NO and (B) N₂O production capacity of *E. meliloti* 1021 (grey bars) and Sm4002
434 strains (black bars) incubated for 24 hours in MMN under anoxic conditions. Bars
435 represent the means with the standard deviations obtained using the Tukey HSD test at
436 $P \leq 0.05$ from at least two different cultures assayed in triplicate.

437

438

Figure 1

439

440

Figure 2

441

Figure 2

A)

B)

